

Green Entrepreneurial Orientation, Green Innovation and Competitive Advantage among Small and Medium Enterprises: The New Entrepreneurial Revolution

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Abstract

There is growing concern about environment. In view of significant socio-economic contribution of SMEs across countries, this sector plays a key role in achieving ‘net-zero’ carbon emission. Yet, the underlying mechanism of green entrepreneurship is still at its nascent stage and firm posture in the adoption of green concept has not been given ample attention. The study contributes to the wide literature by assessing the effect of green entrepreneurial orientation, the dual nature of green innovation including green radical and green incremental innovation on competitive advantage. The study develops a conceptual framework to assess the relationship among the different variables and competitive advantage in a small economy island, Mauritius. The study uses a structured questionnaire to collect data among SMEs in Mauritius. SPSS was used to conduct descriptive analysis and regression analysis followed by AMOS to conduct structural equation modelling to examine the model. The study found that green entrepreneurial orientation, green incremental innovation directly affects competitive advantage but the direct effect of radical innovation on competitive advantage was not supported. Radical and incremental innovation mediates the relationship of green entrepreneurial orientation on competitive advantage.

Keywords: Green entrepreneurial orientation, green entrepreneurship, green innovation, green innovation, green radical innovation, green incremental innovation, competitive advantage

1 Introduction

During recent decades, the world has witnessed industrial revolution leading to a rise in the standard of living, economic growth, and significant change in technology [60]. On the other side, the planet has experienced severe environmental degradation [59, 26] including greenhouse effect, depletion of ozone layer, environment pollution, release of toxic substance in the atmosphere, heavy carbon emission, natural disasters, [41] deforestation, over use of fossil fuels, and rise in temperature [60, 61]. In this context, institutions have warned that environmental issues have threatened human well-being, and economic growth [48]. Institutions have called upon countries to invest in renewable energy so as to migrate towards sustainable energy that will enable countries to reduce carbon emission significantly [60]. Moreover, enterprises should invest in sustainable food production that will generate healthy future generation and discourage end products related with deforestation [23]. Along the same line, in view of the significant socio-economic contribution of entrepreneurs across countries, small and medium enterprises (SMEs) have not been spared by their contribution regarding environmental challenges. The report [48] stressed on the role of SMEs to realise the policy of ‘net zero’ in greenhouse effect. This implies that SMEs play a key role to address the environment challenge and to subsequently move towards a green business model. Hence, entrepreneurs should transit towards green products, process, and technology to mitigate the environment challenge.

The growing environmental concern and its relationship with industries and human related activities [18, 48] has given rise to a plethora of literatures on eco-friendly approaches among industrialists. Studies have shown the importance of different variables among corporates that play a key role to overcome the environmental challenge. However, previous literatures have not provided ample attention towards green posture among Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs), that is, green entrepreneurial orientation (GEO) and green innovation in the concept of green entrepreneurship. The objective of the present research is to fill this void by expanding our knowledge about green entrepreneurial orientation and green innovation on competitive advantage among SMEs. Moreover, the dichotomous nature of green innovation including green radical innovation (Green RINN) and

green incremental innovation (Green ININN) have rarely been studied. The present research studies the variables in a single model and demonstrates the importance of those variables in reducing environmental impact.

2 Research Background

2.1 Green Entrepreneurial Orientation

Green Entrepreneurial Orientation (GEO) is the firm level posture to integrate green practices at every organisational function aiming to address environmental challenges as posited by [27]. The writers stated that GEO is founded at the interface of Entrepreneurial Orientation and Green Entrepreneurship while earlier [36] stated that GEO is the integration of firm initiative towards green engagement to preserve the environment. [27:2] define GEO as “firm-level proactive strategic inclination to identify and grasp the eco-friendly business opportunity based on the comprehensive consideration of risks and benefits”. In the same vein, [24] argued that sustainability oriented entrepreneurs are willing to look for green opportunities and act upon it by integrating green activities in their production, process, technology, and final products [58]. [36] argued that the adoption of green entrepreneurial posture also implies proactive behaviour that is reflected in green ventures. Similarly, [38] showed that exposure to sustainability opportunities lead to sustainable entrepreneurial position. Thus, it implies that GEO is embedded in green entrepreneurship theory and it plays a key role to overcome environment challenges. Despite its importance in green entrepreneurship taxonomy, GEO has not received ample attention in the academic literatures. The present study fills this void by investigating firm level green posture and its effect on competitive advantage among SMEs.

Moreover, few studies on GEO have focussed on the triple bottom line including the dimensions of environment, social, and economy [45,38]. [8] studied the social and innovative posture of GEO. In contrast, [27] argued that GEO should not be looked at solely for the triple bottom line but should also be based on pioneered EO studies by scholars such as [42] and [19]. The latter argued about the multi-dimensions of proactiveness, risk-taking, opportunity seeking, and competitive aggressiveness [62].

[24] argued that sustainability oriented entrepreneurs are willing to look for green opportunities and integrate them in their production process and technology leading to the creation of green products. Similarly, [36] argued that the adoption of green posture also implies proactive behaviour reflected in green ventures whereas [38] demonstrated that exposure to sustainability opportunities lead to sustainable entrepreneurial position at firm level. Thus, the current study posits that green oriented entrepreneurs look for green opportunities and implement them in their daily activities in the form of process, technology or final product to achieve different degree of innovation ranging from incremental to radical innovation. For instance, a green firm will look for opportunities to reduce level of carbon emission or decrease pollution emitted in the atmosphere; while other firms may seize opportunity of the green market by venturing in organic products. Moreover, in line with [63] the present study posits that green oriented firms will undertake risk to invest in green technology, make incremental or radical changes in the process or introduce green products with a chance of high return. Most research has focussed on the behavioural aspects of green entrepreneurial orientation. Few studies demonstrated that GEO influences financial performance [36], environmental performance, [25, 53] or competitive advantage [13, 51]. Again few studies have displayed the combine effect of GEO and green innovation [27,45].

H₁: Green entrepreneurial orientation has direct positive relationship on competitive advantage

2.2 Green Innovation

Previous literature and report have demonstrated that innovation fuels the growth of economy [31, 48]. Another school of thought, claimed that green innovation (GI) is crucial to address the global environment crises to transcend towards a greener economy (60, 61, 2) and create social value [6]. Subsequently, GI has gained ground in the green entrepreneurship literature and research claims that integrating GI in the strategic framework mitigates environment degradation [15, 33, 3]. In this view, scholars and commissions have attempted to define GI as: “innovation that incorporates novelty in the holistic business model, starting from the production process

until disposal that enables an enterprise to migrate towards a greener economy throughout its life cycle” [11:1075,48:3].

This implies all aspects in an organisation should move towards sustainability that includes:

Green production process embodies adoption of technology that reduces carbon emission, emission of toxic substances in the atmosphere, prevents environment pollution, and use more renewable resources in production process.

Product starting from acquisition of bio raw material as input towards the end product that incorporates green attributes until disposal.

Green packaging is packaging that is biodegradable, can be reused or recycled, for example regulation introduced in Mauritius regarding banning of plastic bags to protect the environment led manufacturers to launch environment friendly packaging that are biodegradable.

Though GI has gained importance among firms yet research on the topic is still nascent. Despite few literatures have studied the dimensions of product and process innovation [12, 17, 3] yet the study of bipolar dimensions of green radical and green incremental innovation in the green entrepreneurship literature has rarely been seen [15, 1, 21]. The current study aims to fill the void in the literature by studying the two continuum of green innovation among SMEs.

The current study attempts to define green radical and green incremental innovation from [34:3] and [15: 7789]. The authors defined green RI to ‘incorporate revolutionary changes departing from existing products, services, processes to embrace the integration of green concept using green technology that reduces environment degradation and creates value to end customer’ and green ININN that involves the ‘adjustment, improvement or refinement of existing products, services, processes to embody green features, attributes and knowledge using green technology to reduce environment degradation’. Few scholars have attempted to study green radical and incremental innovation [15, 21, 54]. Few studies demonstrated the effect of green innovation including green product, process innovation on competitive advantage [17, 12, 55], green competitive advantage [16] or organisational performance [10, 33]. Yet, the study of green RINN and green ININN on competitive advantage has rarely been studied [1]. The current study aims to study green radical and incremental innovation in the green entrepreneurship concept and the relationship on competitive advantage.

H₂: Green radical innovation has direct positive relationship on competitive advantage

H₃: Green incremental innovation has direct positive relationship on competitive advantage

2.3 Competitive Advantage

[40] argued that competitive advantage emanates from the resource-based view theory, that is, if firms possess resources that are rare, valuable, inimitable or non-substitutable [4, 5] then the firm gains competitive advantage in the industry. Competitive advantage also depends on the capabilities possessed by firms such as skills, knowledge, marketing capabilities which subsequently generates competitive advantage [37].

In the same vein, [18] argued that previously CA was based on economies of scale or firms offering low price [40] while in the present era, CA is based on value creation or firms offering superior value than competitors. [50] revealed that CA displays two dimensions including cost leadership and differentiation. Whereby, the present study argues that firms adopting an environmental friendly posture generates CA in the market and that GEO, Green radical and incremental innovation provides firms with competitive advantage.

H₄: Green radical innovation mediates the relationship of GEO on competitive advantage

H₅: Green incremental innovation mediates the relationship of GEO on competitive advantage

3 Research Framework

After studying the wide literature on green entrepreneurship, the objective of the current study is to address the theoretical gap in existing literature by studying the relationship between GEO, green radical and incremental innovation on competitive advantage among SMEs. The study further examines a conceptual model incorporating GEO with green RINN and green ININN as mediator on competitive advantage. Though previous literatures have studied GEO in green entrepreneurship, yet the joint relationship of GEO and Green innovation has rarely been studied. Moreover, green innovation including green radical and incremental innovation as a mediator on GEO among small enterprises has not been seen. The current study fills this void and proposes a conceptual framework to assess the joint effect of GEO, GRINN and Green ININN in a single model.

Fig. 1: Conceptual Framework

4 Context of Study

Mauritius is a small economy tropical island located in the Indian Ocean. The estimated population is 1.2 million with a broad ethnic diversity. The economy had undergone different stages of development from primary sector of agriculture particularly sugar to manufacturing during the industrial revolution. Recently, the country has shifted to service-oriented economy mainly the tourism sector, health sector, financial services, information, and computer technology sector [64]. In the same vein, small and medium enterprises (SMEs) represents a significant share of the economy.

Survey conducted by [56] showed that SMEs represent a contribution of 40 percent GDP of the island with 252 400 employees working in the industry and 108 000 unit of SMEs operating. The SME Mauritius defines SME in Mauritius as micro enterprise with an annual turnover not exceeding 10 million; small enterprise with an annual turnover exceeding 10 million but not exceeding 30 million and medium enterprise as turnover exceeding 30 million but not exceeding 100 million.

Moreover, despite the economy has experienced favourable economic transition [57, 64] the island has not been spared by climatic change manifested as vulnerability to rise in sea levels, variations in temperature, extreme weather events, and fluctuations in rainfall [35]. Subsequently, the government has enforced several laws regarding environment protection [43] and the Ministry of Environment has implemented projects to transcend towards a greener economy. SMEs have been integrated in projects to reduce waste, encourage recycling of materials, use green energy, reduce pollution and adopt green technology and green process [44].

5 Methodology and Data Collection

5.1 Measurement and Constructs

The study adopts a quantitative method using a structured questionnaire for data collection. Constructs to assess independent variables and dependent variables were designed after thorough study of the literature review and were adapted from empirical studies. Measurement items in the questionnaire followed Likert scales of 1 to 5 ranging from strongly disagree to strongly agree where 1 represented a weak posture of the variable and 5 represented the strongest posture of the variable. Measurement constructs for independent variables comprises green innovation and green entrepreneurial orientation while dependent variable is competitive advantage. The study identifies two types of innovation namely green radical innovation and green incremental innovation whereby measurement items are derived from the study of [1]. Green radical innovation consisted 5 items and

green incremental innovation consisted 6 items to measure the respective constructs. Green entrepreneurial innovation is new to the literature and therefore there are few reliable scales to measure the construct green EO for the current study. Therefore, items used to measure the construct of EO was designed after studying research from [36] and [45]. The two measures were combined into 6 items to measure EO. The dependent variable, competitive advantage was designed using 6 items based on scales developed by [52].

5.2 Sampling and Data Collection

Data was collected from SMEs in Mauritius operating in different sectors. List of SMEs was taken from the directory of Enterprise Mauritius. The study focussed on manufacturing sectors including Food and Beverage, Leather and Garments, Bioorganic and Medical, Handicraft, furniture and the Agricultural industry. Manufacturing sector is key to carbon emission, pollution and the use of raw material. Subsequently, the transition towards environment friendly activities such as the adoption of green technology, use of renewable resources will enable to transit towards green economy. The Handicraft sector was included because these enterprises use recycling materials in the production process. Sample was selected based on judgement from the list respecting the threshold defined by SME Mauritius and which satisfied the selection criteria for the study. Respondents selected for the questionnaire were employees who were aware about the green concept being implemented in the enterprise and included owner-managers, factory or operation manager, marketing officers, general manager, supervisor and administrative persons. Firms were contacted by telephone to explain the objective of the study and to seek an appointment. 200 firms were contacted by telephone and 50 firms agreed to participate in the study, yielding a response rate of 20 percent. Data collection from SME is challenging and the same can be experienced in Mauritius. Therefore, to increase the response rate convenience sampling strategy was adopted. SME fairs were visited and owner-managers were approached, the purpose of the study was explained and they were requested to fill the questionnaire. Face-to-face survey was adopted in all cases so that clarity can be provided in case the respondent has difficulty to understand the questions. At the end of the study 104 duly filled questionnaires were collected.

6 Results and Findings

6.1 Profile of respondents

Data was collected from SMEs in Mauritius targeting the manufacturing industry, agricultural sector, printing and digital firms. Data was collected for a period of one year and ended with a sample of 104 duly filled questionnaire. The demographic profile of enterprise and respondents is shown in table 1:

Table 1: Profile of Respondents

Sector	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Food & Beverage	26	25
Leather & Garments	23	22.1
Furniture & Wood	15	14.4
Printing & Digital	5	4.8
Handicraft	15	14.4
Agriculture	7	6.7
Bioorganic, Green energy	12	11.6
Plastic & Chemicals	1	1.0
Role of respondent		
Owner-manager	58	55.8
Factors/operation manager	6	5.8
Marketing & admin management	23	22.0
Interior design	11	10.6
Account/finance	1	1.0
6	5.8	
Gender		
Male	59	56.7
female	45	43.3
Highest level of education		
Primary level	5	4.8
Secondary level	40	38.5
Undergraduate/professional	40	38.5
Postgraduate	16	15.4
Vocational	3	2.9

Sales Level		
< 5M	51	49.0
5M – 10 M	21	20.2
>10 M – 20 M	7	6.7
>20 M – 30 M	9	8.7
>30 M – 40 M	2	1.9
>40 – 50 M	8	7.7
>50 M	6	5.8

6.2 Analysis of constructs

The reliability of scales for each constructs were assessed using firstly Cronbach alpha reliability test. using SPSS. Cronbach alpha for GEO displayed value of 0.806. One item from green RINN was deleted ‘our firm invest in modern technologies to create new green products’ and subsequently reliability test yielded value of 0.771. further, green ININN construct displayed value of 0.806 and 1 item from competitive advantage ‘our enterprise is more profitable than competitors’ was removed leading to a value of 0.833. All constructs demonstrated an acceptance reliability value above 0.7 [28]. Table below shows the Cronbach alpha values and descriptive analysis values of each construct.

Table 2: Descriptive analysis of constructs

Constructs	Items	Mean	SD	Skewness	Kurtosis	Cronbach
GEO	7	3.8	0.58	-0.59	0.57	0.806
Green RINN	5	3.8	0.54	-0.077	0.048	0.771
Green ININN	6	3.88	0.52	0.099	-0.57	0.806
CA	5	3.81	0.56	0.12	-0.42	0.833

Moreover, linear regression was performed to examine the direct effect of independent variables GEO, green RINN, green ININN on the dependent variable competitive advantage. The direct relationship of GEO on competitive advantage was significant (sig.=0.00) and adjusted R-square was 0.491 thus accounting 49.1% of the model. Further, the direct relationship of incremental innovation was significant (sig. = 0.00) and adjusted R-square of 0.605 or accounting for 60.5% of the model.

6.3 The Measurement Model

Secondly, the current study followed 2 steps process to test the structural model using AMOS. Firstly, the measurement model was tested and confirmatory factor analysis was employed to evaluate the reliability of scales followed by examining the structural model. [46] suggested flexibility regarding cut-off criteria and that for smaller sample size value of comparative fit index (CFI) close to 0.95 should be acceptable while [29] stated that RMSEA between 0.05 and 0.08 shows a fair fit model. Two items from the construct GEO including GEO3 and GEO4 was removed since factor loadings were less than 0.5 while all other items displayed value of more than 0.5 in the measurement model. In the same line the measurement value displayed value of RMSEA 0.07, being less than 0.8 represents a good fit of the model. Comparative fit index (CFI) yielded value 0.9, Tucker Lewis Index (TLI) 0.9, Goodness-of-fit index 0.81, PCFI 0.81 while the measurement model was significant (p-0.00; DF – 183).

6.4 The Structural Model

The second step employed was to assess the structural model. The structural model displayed RMSEA value of 0.07 indicating a fair fit of the model. According to [32] value close to 0.00 shows a good fit of the model while value of 0.05 to 0.08 shows a fair fit of the model. The structural model shows a significant value of 0.00 (DF = 225). Moreover, the model showed Normed fit index value 0.8, Comparative fit index 0.90, Tucker Lewis index 0.90. The model also showed that the direct path green radical innovation on competitive advantage is not significant while all the other paths are significant. Results also showed that H1, that is the direct relationship of GEO on CA is significant (p value-0.00). Hypotheses H₃ which explains the direct effect of GININN on CA is also significant (p value- 0.00) but the hypotheses H₂, the direct effect of RINN on CA is not supported (p value – 0.60). The model showed that GEO is mediated by GININN and GRINN on Competitive advantage and hence

the hypotheses H₄ and H₅ are supported. The study therefore demonstrates that green innovation including different degree is important to adopt an eco-friendly posture.

Fig. 2: The Structural Model

7 Discussion and Conclusion

The study was conducted among SMEs in the Mauritian context. A conceptual model was constructed to test the relationship between the independent variables, mediating variables and dependent variables. The constructs green EO, green RINN, green ININN and competitive advantage were integrated in a single model.

The current study revealed that SMEs integrate an innovative posture to transcend towards green practices in their daily operation. Grants and loans offered at low interest rate by banks are opportunities for entrepreneurs to venture in green business. In line with [63], entrepreneurs undertake risk by investing in the development of sustainable product lines and technology to reduce environment degradation. For instance, few entrepreneurs have imported new equipment that enable less energy consumption or reduces carbon emission in the atmosphere. Further, following the ban of plastic bags in Mauritius, entrepreneurs have seized this opportunity to produce and commercialise eco-friendly bags and biodegradable packaging. However, in line with the study of [9], it seems that SMEs do not adopt an aggressive competitive posture and they prefer to work for themselves without paying attention to competitor's activities.

Consistent with [14, 15] the current study revealed that entrepreneurs have integrated the use of environmental friendly raw material in the production process. That is, raw materials used in production process comprises recycled, re-used, biodegradable or bio materials in the production of creative, novel end-products. Further, in line with the [61] recommendation, SMEs have invested in the use of green renewable energy such as photovoltaic cells to migrate towards sustainable enterprise. The use of green energy such as implementation of photovoltaic cells in the daily operation is embedded in the green entrepreneurship concept in Mauritius since the government has provided owner-managers with financial facilities to move towards the use of green energy.

[1, 13] demonstrated that green innovation allows enterprises to differentiate themselves leading to competitive advantage. In contrast, the current study showed that the hypothesis H₂ is not supported and that the direct effect of radical innovation on competitive advantage is not significant. This may be explained by the fact that there is lack of awareness about environment challenges among Mauritian population or else the existence of completely new green products, process or technology are unknown to final customers. In contrast, the hypothesis H₃ is supported showing that green incremental innovation has a positive relationship on competitive advantage. It could be seen that SMEs have done minor changes, adjustment or improvement in the

product, packaging, process or technology to make the existing concept green and reduce pollution. It was also seen that incremental changes in process, technology or product lead to competitive advantage. Moreover, to comply with government regulations, entrepreneurs have implemented minor improvement in the packaging of products to make it biodegradable. Few entrepreneurs claimed the implementation of R concept in the routine activity including Recycle, Reduce, and Re-manufacture in the production process.

8 Managerial and Policy Implication

The findings of the current study provide important insights to implement sustainable practices among SMEs. In line with [7], the study reveals that government and institutions should reinforce policies to orient towards a sustainable society.

The current research found that it is imperative for the government to provide support to SMEs for the effective implementation of eco-friendly activities. For instance, the Ministry of Environment is working with entrepreneurs from medium enterprises to implement sustainability project and promote the use of green energy. It is recommended that the project be extended on a larger scale and among smaller counterparts. Moreover, financial assistance, including grants and low interest loans, are essential to re-engineer enterprises towards green technology, green process, and the development of completely new green products.

Green entrepreneurial orientation and green innovation allows firms to reduce cost and create superior value to customers, leading to competitive advantage. The study recommends entrepreneurs to integrate sustainable development in their operation. Incumbents should innovate to migrate towards the adoption of green technology to decrease pollution. The study revealed that recycling and re-use enables the society to cut down on waste for example textile and handicraft enterprises use remaining of raw materials in the production process to commercialise creative products.

Additionally, it is recommended to conduct awareness campaign among the general population to enhance the use of green products. Owner-managers should comply to policies and incumbents should be willing to re-engineer the enterprise towards environmental friendly tasks and activities.

9 Limitation of Study and Further Research

The current study has some limitations. For instance, the study follows quantitative cross-sectional method among 104 small and medium enterprises. The study can be extended to a greater number of firms to get more insights. The study can also be complemented by qualitative study including focus group to generate more findings and ideas about actions that can be taken by the government and institutions to motivate entrepreneurs transcend towards environmental friendly activities.

Abbreviations: GI-Green innovation, green RINN – green radical innovation, Green ININN-green incremental innovation, CA- competitive advantage

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Table 3: Measures for constructs

Green Entrepreneurial Orientation (Jiang et al., 2018; Muangmee, et al., 2021)	
GEO1	In general, our firm favours a strong emphasis on green practices, such as R & D, technological leadership, and innovation
GEO2	When facing uncertainty, we typically adopt a proactive posture in order to catch potential green opportunities.
GEO3	"In dealing with competitors, we typically initiate green actions that competitors do."
GEO4	"In dealing with competitors, we typically adopt a competitive 'undo-the-competitors' posture."
GEO5	Our organization uses less or non-polluting/toxic materials.
GEO6	Our organization has a strong tendency for high risk green product development projects which have a chance of high returns.
GEO7	"Our organization has a tendency to be a market leader, always first in introducing green products, services, or technologies"
Green Innovation	
Green radical innovation (GRINN) - Al-Khatib, A. (2022)	
RINN1	"Our firm invents a new generation of green innovations in its products and services."
RINN2	Our firm invest in modern technologies to create new green products.
RINN3	"Our firm is making new radical organizational changes that reflect its orientation towards innovations."
RINN4	"Our firm is interested in introducing new experiences that did not exist before in terms of green technology."
RINN5	Our firm focuses on new environmental ideas.
RINN6	Our firm creates new green distribution channels.
Green incremental innovation (GIINN)	
GIINN1	Our firm is working on minor changes to existing green products and services.
GIINN2	Our firm is constantly making improvements to its green operations.
GIINN3	"Our firm encourages employees to generate new ideas supporting its green innovations."
GIINN4	"Our firm encourages staff to hold regular meetings to listen to the best ways to make improvements to existing green products."
GIINN5	"Our firm periodically improves and maintains production lines to reduce waste and pollution risks."
GIINN6	Our firm has effective and efficient waste recycling systems.
Competitive advantage (Qiu et al., 2018)	

CA1	The quality of products or services offered by our enterprise is of better/higher quality than that of competitors.
CA2	The enterprise is more capable of R & D than competitors.
CA3	The enterprise has better managerial capability than competitors.
CA4	Our enterprise is more profitable than competitors.
CA5	Our enterprise has a better corporate image than our competitors.
CA6	The competitive advantage of our enterprise is difficult to replace by competitors.

Fig. 2: Measurement Model

